

Geopolitics of Energy

Artur Victoria

Geopolitics, as a method of studying international relations, highlights the importance of location factors over relations between countries. Thus, geopolitics considers geographical factors as important determinants of government policy and the relative position of power of nations. In this energy study, these localization factors are examined, of course, when we consider access to raw materials in general.

In turn, the importance of several geographical factors is a function of many parameters. such as time, technological discoveries, the need for raw materials, national and international objectives and the ethics of international relations.

Furthermore, the importance of geographic and location factors also varies according to the international system itself; new international ties come on the scene (both new countries and multinational corporations, international organizations and regional economic and military organizations); the legitimacy and suitability of traditional actors, of the nation-states themselves, are subject to debate. Power becomes more diluted; superpowers are often embarrassed by smaller countries that find room to manoeuvre within the impasse created by atomic arsenals. Interdependence, both in terms of mutual dependence and interpenetration, is a reality. in this dynamic international environment that geopolitics is access to raw materials have to evolve.

Are there geopolitical factors related to the supply of energy and raw materials that indicate the direction that international relations should take in the coming decades? Which areas, through

What combination of countries will these geographic factors make likely? If energy is of vital interest to the world community, will there be “energy centres”, like the Middle East today, on which the rest of the world will depend?

As all primary energy sources depend on a set of additional measures necessary to transform energy into a usable form and transport it to areas of consumption, factors other than the geographic distribution of resources are essential aspects of energy geopolitics. Supply lines, technology and processing facilities, without which raw resources are worth almost nothing, will also have implications for international policy.

Finally, the continued interaction between the factors that influence supply (processing reserves, new discoveries, increased energy consumption and energy research and technology) and the factors that influence demand (economic growth, needs of a particular economic system, and availability of substitutes), which over time changes the relative importance of different resources and geographical factors, is also an important aspect of energy geopolitics.

National interest and National security

Despite efforts to define the needs and energy policy of the countries we do not yet have a national energy policy that is both comprehensive, realistic and acceptable to all. The Government's proposals are the latest in a series of efforts to deal with our energy dependence. We cannot be sure that the final plan will be more comprehensive than previous initiatives. We are not alone in this, as very few industrialized countries in the world today have a global energy policy.

Energy goals have been lost in many other concerns and in a maze of domestic politics. Over time, Governments has shown that it has the capacity to learn and recognize the implications of our increasing dependence on imported oil. Not so recently, energy "initiatives" and "policies" reflected tactical actions aimed at achieving short-term goals, an immediate approach to a very important national problem.

In defining and programming a more appropriate energy policy, countries become more aware of the extent to which energy dependence in international trade affects the choice of allies, changes alliances and, in certain cases, creates the need for new alliances.

The geological "accidents" that concentrated energy resources in pre-industrial societies bring the general question of "North-South" relations to the search for access, a search in which the US may find itself in dispute with traditional allies, or committed in such divergent objectives that they may affect the durability of our relationships.

Government interests

Countries that depend on imported energy resources have two main objectives:

- First, to adopt policies designed to ensure access to additional external supplies that are essential to their national needs;
- Second, reduce the need for access to external supplies.

To ensure access to external supplies, a government has several options: it can seek bilateral relations with major producers; can create a system of preferred suppliers; it can participate in more general movements such as the Common Market-Arab Country dialogue or trade agreements such as the Lomé Convention; can offer technological assistance; or it can participate in even broader international efforts, such as the International Energy Agency (IEA) and the International Economic Cooperation Conference (ECC). You can, of course, do all of this at the same time.

To reduce the need for access to external supplies, a government can implement conservation policies, offer incentives for the development of energy alternatives,

encourage research, etc. These are essentially internal measures that a government can take to reduce demand and stimulate production. The success of these policies will be determined by the timeliness of the measures, the decision with which they are adopted, the current economic policies and the availability of natural energy resources in the country.

The issue of access to energy resources actually involves three interests, which are shared by all energy-deprived countries:

1. The supply of imported energy must be sufficient; there is a level of imports below which national security is put at risk.
2. The supply of imported energy must be continuous. Disruptions or cuts in supply can have serious political and economic repercussions in industrialized countries. Naturally, it is this vulnerability to supply disruptions that gives consumers supplying states a powerful weapon against countries that depend on imported energy.
3. Imported energy must be obtained at “reasonable” prices

The most difficult it is to define the three aspects of access. It is evident that the price paid must bear some relation to the cost of alternative forms of energy both available and planned. The price should also reflect the fact that current sources of energy are not renewable and their reserves are decreasing. The price must also reflect an “ability to pay”.

These three factors - a sufficient and continuous supply at a reasonable price - constitute an indissoluble trio of energy interests. The lack of any of these factors can have disastrous consequences for the economic welfare, political stability and national security of the consuming country.

Contemporary energy geopolitics

The twentieth century witnessed the biggest shift in energy sources the world has perhaps experienced since the use of fire was widespread. In the first twenty-five years of the century, coal was arguably the main source of energy for the industrialized world. The energy needs of large countries could be met entirely by domestic resources or supplemented by sources close by (in the case of Japan). Coal would have continued to be the main source of energy if the discovery of large quantities of oil in southern Russia, the Middle East and, later, in the United States, had not quickly aroused interest in the comparative ease of its extraction and transportation, and its conversion to meet a wide range of needs.

What circumstances caused the oil revolution in the mid-fifties? What circumstances led to your availability being placed at the top of national priorities? These questions can be illustrated by statistical references to the increase in energy consumption,

starting in 1960 (the year in which the Organization of the Petroleum Exporting Countries [OPEC) was founded); that year, world energy consumption was of the order of 132 quintillion British Thermal Units (QBTU); ten years later, it was 217 QBTU; five years later, in 1975, it reached about 225 QBTU. In 1990, the 415 QBTU - a three-fold increase in world energy consumption in just thirty years.

What was the share of oil (and natural gas) in these increases? In 1960, they accounted for 48 percent of the world's energy consumption. Ten years later, participation had increased to 63 percent; in 1975, it was already 67 percent; and in 1990, even if we assume a large contribution from nuclear energy, the share of oil and natural gas reaches 85 percent.

The implications in terms of quantity are impressive. Eight billion barrels of oil consumed worldwide in 1960, 17 billion barrels in 1975, and 30 billion barrels in 1980: an almost four-fold increase in oil and gas consumption.

Ten years later, participation had increased to 63 percent; in 1975, it was already 67 percent; and in 1990, even if we assume a large contribution from nuclear energy, the share of oil and natural gas reaches 85 percent.

The implications in terms of quantity are impressive. Eight billion barrels of oil consumed worldwide in 1960, 17 billion barrels in 1975, and 30 billion barrels in 1980: an almost four-fold increase in oil and gas consumption in thirty years.

Coal, on the other hand, which had been the main source of energy, was still responsible for 47 percent of the world's energy consumption in 1960, but fell to 30 percent in 1976.

Thus, the convenience of oil, the fact that it requires a minimum amount of labour, the extraordinary number of applications and, perhaps most important of all, the fact that it is relatively cheap, plus the huge increase in production, and the discovery of immense deposits - everything combined to make oil and its derivatives the most desirable and most important form of energy.

The decision that would take oil, years later, to take first place as an energy source was taken before the First World War, when the British Admiralty decided to convince its war squadron to consume oil, a decision quickly imitated by all the great powers of the time. This measure resulted in a whole series of geopolitical factors: access to oil imposed new and important commitments to foreign and defence policies. For the English especially, given the size and role of the Royal Navy, the Middle East, which was still considered the "bridge" to India and the East, a bridge to be defended against the Russians' ambitions, took on another meaning strategic: access to Iran and the Persian Gulf oil fields.

Before World War II, French, German and American interests were also looking for access to oil. Although the strategic importance of oil may have weighed, it was not necessarily the predominant factor that led these countries to become interested in the Middle East.

In the case of Germany, the desire to obtain a strategic advantage over England may have been more important than oil itself. Likewise, the traditional rivalry between France and England may have been the original reason for the French presence 'in the Middle East, which in any case was not based on an urgent need for oil.

In the case of the United States, commercial interests were the most important. Perhaps it was mainly in the case of Japan (which, however, sought its supplies in Southeast Asia) that the recognition of the strategic importance of the oil supply motivated external activities.

After World War II, the threat of Soviet expansion in the Middle East and the creation of Israel added new dimensions to American interests. The growing importance attached to oil in the international energy trade has rapidly expanded the list of American concerns. However, the United States has not discussed the long-term implications of this sharp interest in oil in general, nor its exclusive access to Saudi Arabian oil.

This is true even today, although the allies and others find it ridiculous that the United States continues to explain that there is no "special relationship" as to the immense oil reserves of that kingdom, on whose policy the energy interests of so many depend.

Industrialized nations in general have not had energy policies appropriate to their degree of dependence. It is not surprising, therefore, that in the early 1960s, when oil consumption really began to soar and rank high on the list of nations' strategic interests, political changes in producing countries destroyed the imperialist system; control of oil passed to the other side. The change was too rapid to allow industrialized countries to calmly examine the alternatives available to them to recover the necessary guarantee of supply.

Energy needs change

The exponential growth in the need for imported energy from the large industrialized countries is the basic condition that initiates a discussion of energy geopolitics. Three sets of data illustrate the situation:

- (1) The increase in energy consumption in these countries;
- (2) The extent to which these needs have been met by oil and oil imports;
- (3) The importance of the Middle East and Africa as suppliers.

Oil sources

The immense reserves from which the world draws its oil are limited to a small number of countries. Since the beginning of modern use of oil, the largest reserves have been found in the Middle East; the largest producers, until recently, were the United States and the Soviet Union. Currently, the Russia it seems to be in the lead, with Saudi Arabia quickly closing the gap (with more than 9 million barrels per day [MBD]) and having no technical difficulties to overcome the Russian Federation.

However, oil in world trade - which is the essential point, as it meets the needs of importing countries - has been predominantly that of the Middle East. Today, that oil makes up about 75 percent of oil in international trade.

Reserves indicate the volume of oil in a given field, country or region that can be extracted profitably at current prices and with available technology.

Production capacity is the amount of oil that can be extracted with existing production facilities. The reserves of the main producers (with the current levels of production and the "reserve capacity" indicated) and their participation in the world oil trade provide the most complete view of the current importance of these countries. OPEC members dominate the world's oil; its production is about 30 MBD. Communist countries produced 12 MBD and the rest of the world another 16 MBD.

OPEC oil reserves ("estimated" and probable) also dominate: almost 480 billion barrels, compared with 65 billion barrels in communist countries and 120 billion barrels in the rest of the world. Among the OPEC countries, the nations of the Persian Gulf occupy a special position. They are responsible for 23 MBD (and have the capacity to produce 28 MBD); its reserves are currently in the order of 365 billion barrels.

Transport requirements

There are three basic requirements for the supply of oil:

Production, transport and refining. Current oil production for world trade is, for all practical purposes, under the political control of the OPEC countries. (Canada is currently the only exception, but the government's official policy has been to decrease exports to meet domestic consumption.) "Control" is not absolute, of course, but the role of governments in producing countries in control of production levels is unprecedented in history.

Oil transportation is currently under the control of countries that are not part of OPEC. The vast majority of oil tankers are owned or leased to an international oil company. In

the event of supply cuts, these ships are still under sufficient control to comply with the companies' instructions.

As for tonnage, it proved to be adequate in the three major crises of 1956, 1967 and 1973, but it was insufficient in 1970. It is more than adequate in 1980, including smaller ships that are needed for North American ports; current tonnage surpluses are on the order of 40 percent.

The former Soviet Union appears to have enough oil tankers to meet its needs and external commitments. OPEC countries hold no more than 3 percent of the tonnage of oil tankers in world trade.

Pipelines are found mainly within the United States, Canada, Europe and the Soviet Union. They are ingredients as essential elements for the safe and continuous supply of oil and natural gas. None of them, of course, is under the control of an OPEC member country.

Only oil and gas pipelines that supply Europe with Russian oil and gas should be considered today as vulnerable to disruption for political reasons or economic war. Iran's oil pipelines and the system through which Iraq and Saudi Arabia supply oil to the eastern Mediterranean countries are under the exclusive control of the importing country (or are shared in transit).

None of them are essential (because of the small volumes of oil and the existence of alternative routes and terminals) for international oil trade. The installation of Saudi Arabia's new pipeline to the Red Sea is unlikely to change the situation.

Supply vulnerabilities in the current logistics system are related to:

(1) the contribution to Europe's energy from oil and gas produced by the former Soviet Union or transiting through that country; and

(2) The quantitative and qualitative composition of the world tanker fleet.

With reference to the first item, the supplies of the former U.R.S.S. they were not expressive, by any criterion, but they are obviously a factor that must be observed in the future, especially in relation to natural gas.

None of them, of course, is under the control of an OPEC member country. Only oil and gas pipelines that supply Europe with Russian oil and gas should be considered today as vulnerable to disruption for political reasons or economic war.

Iran's oil pipelines and the system through which Iraq and Saudi Arabia supply oil to the eastern Mediterranean countries are under the exclusive control of the importing country (or are shared in transit).

None of them are essential (because of the small volumes of oil and the existence of alternative routes and terminals) for international oil trade. The installation of Saudi Arabia's new pipeline to the Red Sea is unlikely to change the situation.

Supply vulnerabilities in the current logistics system are related to:

(1) The contribution to Europe's energy from oil and gas produced by the former Soviet Union or transiting through that country; and

(2) The quantitative and qualitative composition of the world tanker fleet. With reference to the first item, the supplies of the former U.R.S.S. they were not expressive, by any criterion, but they are obviously a factor that must be observed in the future, especially in relation to natural gas. In the case of oil tankers, the trend towards larger and more specialized vessels may in the future reduce the flexibility of the logistics system.

As for refineries, the processing capacity of the main energy consuming countries is currently more than sufficient. They all have a network of refineries capable of meeting their energy needs (in the case of the United States, the important Antilles refineries are considered "safe"). The expressed intentions of the oil producing countries to start refining the product themselves until today do not materialize.

Refineries are controlled by industrialized countries. In the supply of refined oil, only the Antilles refineries raise transport security issues; almost all oil in world trade is transported as crude oil.

Furthermore, no OPEC parent individually represents an important segment of world oil consumption; even taken together, these countries do not consume a significant amount: the total consumption of OPEC countries is in the order of 2 MBD. OPEC's large oil markets are concentrated in industrialized countries.

The international petroleum industry

The role that oil plays in the global energy landscape should be attributed to private oil companies, especially the "big internationals" whose vast capital, business capacity, application of capital and technology to oil prospecting and exploration, logistics systems, processing facilities and distribution systems were combined in an integrated operation of enormous influence and efficiency.

From the beginning, the control of international oil by British and American companies has been a "constant"; in 1980, it is still possible to observe that there are no "competitors" nearby.

Some competition is offered by ENI, CFP and other state-owned companies in several countries. In addition, many "independent" companies entered the international oil

trade beginning in the 1950s. However, the biggest changes in the international oil industry were caused by direct acts of governments.

In addition to the measures taken by the governments of the producing countries to guarantee control over the destination of their oil, the measures of the governments of the consuming countries to limit the freedom of the international oil companies have been important, lasting and successful, forcing these companies to reveal information about pricing, profits and planning. Thus, both producer and consumer countries have acted to reduce the influence of large international oil companies.

On the other hand, certain functions exercised by the “big ones” continue to be irreplaceable: the control of the world circulation of crude oil and access to the tankers, refineries and markets on the gigantic scale necessary to serve world trade.

The role of these companies as generators of capital has decreased considerably, at least in producing countries. Even research and technology are no longer the privilege of the “big ones”. However, the general application of technology is a very complex undertaking and is still considered to be the exclusive domain of the "Big".

As is the application of this technology in very hostile environments, such as the North Sea, Brazil (deep oil extraction) and Alaska.

Large international companies have lost much of their decision-making power in terms of production volume and prices, and are also beginning to lose the ability to make plans and make commitments independently of the governments of consumer countries. The “big ones” are considered sensitive or obedient to their own governments' policies and guidelines; in reality, they are believed to be and have always been instruments of foreign policy.

Depending on the point of view, the fact that companies have never fully served the interests of their governments can be considered as an affirmation of independence or as a consequence of the fact that these governments have never clearly defined their energy interests and the parameters within which the companies would have to operate.

Anyway, the role of companies is still indispensable to all interests, although more limited than before.

Policy of energy dependent countries

There were two phases in the history of these countries' oil policy:

First came the imperialist period, when governments and companies competed for oil concessions; government support for these agreements has always been considered the greatest guarantee of their durability.

Naturally, for international oil companies, yesterday and today dominated by the British and American, the priorities were reversed; their commercial interests were the most important factor; for them.

The rivalries between the countries were aspects of the eternal problem of access to increasing volumes of oil - to be used when necessary. International oil companies have not encouraged their governments to develop energy policies that could limit the freedom of action considered essential for their operations on a global scale. Support or protection from governments? Yes. Guidance or control? Do not.

The second phase - which began in the period between the two world wars - was characterized by the emergence of state oil companies, whose objectives were the following:

(1) To allow national participation in the supply of a product whose importance was becoming vital;

(2) To challenge the English and American monopoly in the world oil trade. In the first objective, the central concern was to increase control over the activities of the main suppliers and to better assess the conditions in which oil was being imported. In the second objective, governments perhaps more for reasons of prestige than to obtain commercial advantages - they encouraged the international activities of national companies.

These two objectives, often interconnected, have increased in importance over the years.

The creation of state oil companies in consuming countries occurred almost simultaneously with the emergence of organizations in producing countries, thus reflecting at least a common interest in the conditions in which world trade develops.

The participation of the governments of the oil producing and importing countries relegated purely commercial factors to the background; the supply of oil has become such an important factor for national security that factors other than the simple market economy have necessarily had to come into play.

As a result, governments today may be willing to use all means at their disposal to ensure an adequate and continuous supply at an acceptable price; from the point of view of producers and consumers, other interests are currently involved in access to oil: military assistance - technology, investments, economic and political objectives, all of which considerably complicate the context in which energy resources are discussed.

In the process, state-owned oil companies in consuming countries began to acquire the ability to act directly or indirectly as policy instruments that reflect a broader range of concerns and are less selfish in helping to fix the commercial terms in which oil is

provided. Nowadays, these terms are almost always established by the state companies of the producing countries, and these conditions can also reflect a very wide range of interests of the producers, of which “trade”, although important, is only one aspect.

Given the existence of these non-commercial aspects of oil, the complexities involved in the process of trying to ensure supply have become evident in the negotiations that led to the creation of the International Energy Agency for importing consuming nations.

The IEA's ostensible purpose was to reach an agreement on the fairest way to divide the oil available in the event of another emergency;

Some measures have already been approved, such as establishing an emergency inventory program that in the future will be able to meet ninety days of consumption. However, since the US government started supporting the creation of the IEA, consumer countries have been concerned (and still are) that if another cut or embargo occurs, the United States is likely to be the main target, and therefore, the participation of other countries in such an agreement will bring more disadvantages than advantages.

Behind the clear hesitation of consumers to commit in advance to sharing oil with others, was the most basic question: Wouldn't the IEA be seen as a “challenge” by producing countries? However, no member of the IEA fails to recognize that diplomacy, politics, energy and the economy are inextricably linked, and that the IEA can do little alone, unless many other measures are taken to persuade producing countries to meet the increasing demand for oil from industrialized countries.

Attempts to do this began in December 1975 in Paris. With the launch of the International Economic Cooperation Conference, an initiative by Saudi Arabia and France, the process of discussing interconnected issues of energy, other primary goods, economic development and financial issues began. The CCEI's theses were initially opposed, and, according to some, permanently by the United States, but were supported by other countries, which considered them, at least, as a way to avoid the “confrontation” and to reach possibly a more satisfactory understanding. , of which reliable access to energy supply was an important part. This is another effort to establish a more satisfactory relationship for both parties between suppliers and consumers of raw materials than the old imperialist system.

The success of CCEI is not insured; great interests are at stake, and it may not be possible to reconcile everyone.

Energy and the Russian Federation

Of all the great industrialized powers, the former U.R.S.S. it is the only one that is currently self-sufficient in terms of energy. (Soviet oil and natural gas production meets current domestic needs. According to known data, the former USSR's internal energy production meets an overall demand of 60 QBTU through a 34 percent coal supply, 23 percent natural gas and 36 percent oil.

The main energy problem that former U.R.S.S. facing is the difficulty of meeting the energy needs of the countries of Eastern Europe, of which it insists on being the main supplier. Current Eastern European oil consumption is 1.8 MBD; Russia supplies 90 percent of the region's imports, mostly from its own resources, and the rest is obtained in North Africa and the Persian Gulf.

The increase in Soviet energy resources involves huge costs. Topographical, logistical and technical difficulties and the long pipeline systems needed to explore the fields of Eastern Siberia will continue to be obstacles to increasing production.

To this day, Russian efforts to acquire current technology (drilling techniques on land and at sea and recovery processes) from oil companies in the West and Japan, which is considered essential for increasing Russia's energy resources, have been unsuccessful. However, the Russians insist.

Estimates of Russian import needs over the next decade range from just over 1 MBD to 9 MBD. We just don't know for sure and we can only say that Russia will probably have to import oil in this decade, until it is able to explore new resources in its territory. Western technology would help ex U.R.S.S. maintain their energy autonomy.

A question about Russia policy that "radical" producer governments have long been on their side in an economic war program against the West and Japan. There have been opportunities for this: the 1956 Suez Crisis, the June War 1967, and the October War (and consequent embargo) in 1973-1974.

Furthermore, it might seem that in all three cases there were more than enough anti-Western sentiments to ensure an increase in Russian influence. In addition, large Russian investments in loans, development projects, equipment and military training in various countries and occasions since World War II - in Iraq, Syria, Egypt and more recently in Somalia and Ethiopia - must have seemed to the Kremlin reason enough to believe it was creating a permanent presence in the Middle East, which it had long sought but which seemed an unattainable goal.

However, none of these initiatives have yielded sufficiently lasting results, even today, to jeopardize the oil supply.

Producer's Country's policies

As for the policy evolution of producing countries, the critical observation is that each oil-exporting country (including almost all small producers) has gone through a variety of colonialist experiences under the control of one of the Western empires; if the country was not a colony in the formal sense of the word, its leaders and people probably considered themselves as colonies.

As in many cases the beginning of oil exploration took place during a neo-colonialist experiment, the nationalization of control over oil extraction was seen by these peoples as the sign of the end of an era. Thus, for virtually all of them, "oil" has a profound effect on their political and economic emancipation.

The list includes Mexico, Venezuela, Algeria, Libya, Iran, Iraq, Kuwait, Indonesia and Malaysia.

By freeing itself from a "colonial" relationship and taking control over oil exploration, Mexico showed the way in 1938, expropriating foreign oil companies. This happened more than sixty years ago, but the situation persists today: it is Mexico that decides what it will do with its oil, not foreigners and foreign interests.

Indonesia was also a pioneer country. General Ibnu was convinced that as long as the colonialist system of concessions prevailed against corrosive internal oil policies they could not be contained. He insisted that a new oil policy was essential, and companies were forced to budge. Service and risk contracts became the general rule and quickly removed the political stigma of Indonesia's foreign oil exploration.

In the case of Nigeria, the exploitation of oil reserves began after political independence, but its attitude today results from the experience as a colony and in a chaotic period after independence, which was further complicated by the machinations of the great powers. Thus, Nigeria's oil policy is based on the belief that economic independence is an essential requirement for political independence, the same belief that motivates other PMOs.

Canada and Australia could be considered exceptions to the rule that links oil to "colonialism", but the reality is different. Anyone who has followed the political evolution of these two countries does not ignore the dominant attitude that their resources are being exploited by foreigners; in both cases, the government believes that the energy industry is at the service of external interests. So, for example, almost 90 percent of Canada's oil is controlled by subsidiaries of North American oil companies.

Remarks about energy

The inevitable dependence of practically all major energy-deprived countries on oil in the Middle East is the fundamental fact. So large is the unused production capacity in

the region (about 5 MBD) at the moment that, if all other sources of oil in world trade were to be extinguished, the large industrialized countries could satisfy all their energy import needs. using only the reserve capacity of the Middle East.

During the past few decades, outside the Middle East and the ex-communist world, no large oil reserves have been discovered, except in Libya, Nigeria, the North Sea, Alaska and Mexico. Currently, the pre-salt discoveries imply costly drilling technologies and are still in an extraction stage at a low level.

An estimate of the time needed to explore “prove” to develop and produce a significant amount of oil for world trade is five to ten years. It is extremely unlikely that these discoveries will result in a production capable of overcoming the increase in world demand for oil and reversing the trend of the reserves / production ratio, in order to ensure supply by the end of the century.

1. It is not likely, therefore, that the importance of Middle Eastern oil will diminish in this decade or even until the end of the century.

2. A ex U.R.S.S. (and neighbouring countries) is not currently a direct candidate for Middle Eastern oil. Competition for oil from the Middle East is between NATO allies and Japan.

3. Currently, OPEC is less important than OPAEP. More precisely, Saudi Arabia's idle production capacity and potential production are the most important. Saudi Arabia currently produces about 9.5 MBD; its current production capacity is estimated at 11.5 MBD; and its potential production can reach 20 MBD or more. Thus, any Saudi decision regarding volumes and prices is very important.

4. The main problem of the Organization of Arab Petroleum Exporting Countries (OPAEP) is the possible diversity of interests in the countries of the Persian Gulf, especially Iraq, Iran, Kuwait, and Saudi Arabia, and the problems and opportunities that this can present to the great industrialized powers.

5. The “special” relations between the United States and Saudi Arabia are by far the most important links between producers and major oil importers. However, Europe and Japan depend much more on Saudi and Iranian oil than the United States, which suggests that the link between the United States and these producing countries may cause some problems in relations with Europe and Japan moreover, given the hostility that exists between Iran and Saudi Arabia, perhaps the United States will find it difficult to maintain a “special” relationship with the two countries.

6. OPEC member countries - all LDCs - control the production of “almost” all the oil in world trade.

7. Producing countries control a significant portion of the sea routes, which start at their terminals and loading facilities and extend across the Persian Gulf, Indian Ocean, Red Sea and Suez, the Mozambique Channel, the Straits of Malacca and Lombok.

This entire route is subject to interference or interruption by producers or PMD, or both.

8. Control of the rest of the logistics system - oil tankers, pipelines and processing facilities (and energy technology) is still in the hands of the industrialized world, as well as the major oil markets. Only about 3 percent of the world's 320 million tonne oil tanker route is currently under the role of OPEC countries. Only the pipelines that transport oil to the tankers' loading terminals are in the hands of these countries; none of those directly serving consumer countries is affected. Consumer countries currently have a large refining capacity and are self-sufficient in this regard.

9. Europe, Japan and the Middle East have ports for super tankers that are sufficient for their current needs. The United States cannot yet fully benefit from the savings provided by the very large crude carriers (VLCC). Since the United States does not have sufficient draft ports, the United States depends on smaller ships, which are not currently manufactured at the same pace as VLCCs.

10. The member countries of the International Energy Agency, through their plan to share the available oil supply in the event of supply disruptions for any reason, may be able to better withstand the effects of supply disruptions or cuts than in the past. At least, the emergency mechanism seems adequate, thus introducing an uncertainty factor in the plans of oil producers.

11. International oil companies continue to play an essential role for both producing countries and consumers, thanks to their logistical systems and access to processing facilities, which allow them to handle large volumes of oil. At least 80 percent of the world oil trade (28 MBD) is the responsibility of these companies. In twenty-four hours, these companies transport about a billion barrels of oil from one location to another.

12. Just when oil became vitally important for industrialized countries, the "control" of access to this resource was taken by the producers of the oil companies of the consuming countries. So far, producers and consumers have not reached any global agreement that guarantees the supply of oil; there was not even a process to elaborate the agreement. Prices are determined by producing countries, and the governments of consuming countries have yet to discover ways to influence them. "Price and volume agreements are still" closed "between companies and producer governments, although conditions are ultimately imposed by the latter.

The geopolitical importance of oil results from two main factors: (1) oil, as a fuel and raw material, is the lifeblood of industrialized economies; (2) oil reserves and production tend to be concentrated in certain less developed countries. Indeed, oil reserves and production are more abundant in a small number of developing countries, while the need for an adequate and continued supply of oil in large volumes is more urgent in developed, industrialized countries.

The importance of oil

Oil will continue to meet most of the global energy needs until the end of the 21st century. However, there is a great possibility that the importance of oil has been underestimated in the forecasts:

1. Petroleum is considered to be the fuel of the “breakthrough” compensating for all deficiencies in the production of alternative energy sources; thus, if there is any delay in the development and production of coal, natural gas and nuclear energy, oil will have to make up for the difference.

2. Forecasts assume that, in the future, GNP growth rates will be lower than historical rates; if in the future the GNP growth rates return to the old trend or exceed the values used in the forecasts, oil will have to meet a greater demand for energy. As forecasts tend to be excessively influenced by current or short-term events, there is a possibility that the assumed growth rates are actually too small.

3. If the drop in oil consumption was more a consequence of the recession than a result of rising prices, the economic recovery will stimulate consumption.

4. If the price of short-term energy alternatives follows world oil prices, incentives for substitution (which may also involve the purchase of new equipment and other initial investments) will be reduced, while incentives to increase domestic production oil prices will become bigger; as a result, the substitution of oil by other sources of energy may be delayed.

5. The crisis mentality that emerged as a result of the 1973 embargo has already subsided, and there seems to be a much lesser sense of urgency regarding the need to develop alternatives to oil, at least for the general public.

In addition, many forecasts depend on the ability of governments to design, enact and implement a comprehensive energy policy. If governments have been unable to do so, as so far, the development of alternative forms of energy may be delayed. As forecasts depend on the implementation of national conservation programs, they can overestimate the degree of political decision existing in industrialized countries. In general, the poor economic performance of industrialized countries has led

governments to keep domestic oil prices below international prices, thus reducing the conservation and incentive effects of rising prices.

The maturation periods associated with the development of alternative or supplementary sources of energy are quite long. The following estimated maturation periods (years between the decision and the start of operations) - probably optimistic - are illustrative:

- Proven field development, but not producing, in the Middle East 1-2 years
- Increased oil field production in the United States 1-3 years
- Oil extraction from the continental shelf, in the United States 9-14 years
- Open pit coal mine 2-4 years
- Underground coal mine 3-6 years
- Oil power plant, geothermal or using synthetic fuels 5 years
- Coal-fired power plant 5-8 years
- Hydroelectric plant 5-8 years
- Oil and natural gas production in new fields in the United States 3-12 years
- Uranium prospecting and mining 8-10 years
- Coal gasification 10-15 years
- Oil sands and shale 5-10 years

The effect of these long maturation periods becomes clearer when we add to these figures the delays in decision making, resulting from ambiguous government policies, and the fact that the start of operations does not correspond to the point of maximum contribution.

All available indications suggest that only after the end of the 21st century and alternative sources of energy - shale oil, oil sands oil, marine, wind, biomass, hydrogen and solar - photo voltaic energy - will begin to contribute significantly to the total energy supply.

Time, in this case, becomes of vital importance. It is quite possible that alternative energy sources will not be developed fast enough or on a sufficient scale to prevent sporadic energy crises and the occurrence of a global oil shortage. It will be difficult to coordinate the many aspects of the oil supply-demand relationship, and sporadic crises can be predicted, starting in the early years of this decade.

Petroleum reservs

In 1980, the Middle East and Africa accounted for 65 percent of the world's proven crude oil reserves (78 percent of the world's proven reserves); however, consumption in the Middle East and Africa accounted for only 5 percent of world consumption. OPEC's reserves constituted 66 percent of the world's proven reserves (80 percent), while OPEC's reserves accounted for 50 percent.

At the same time, North America and Western Europe held only 15 percent of world reserves (Japan had no reserves), but the three regions were responsible for 65 percent of world consumption.

It is extremely unlikely that this pattern will change significantly. On the contrary, the tendency is for reserves to be concentrated in an ever smaller number of countries - that is, the countries of the Persian Gulf as the consumption of industrialized countries increases in relation to their reserves.

The increase in oil reserves in industrialized countries is not likely to be greater than the increase in consumption.

Intensive prospecting, the use of new recovery techniques, the adoption of conservation measures and the reduction of oil consumption will not prevent a decline in the reserves / production ratio. Furthermore, given the long maturation periods between discovery, development and full production, an immediate increase in reserves would only begin to contribute to oil supply from the middle of the next decade.

Categories

With the increase in oil prices, it has become a habit to go beyond waiting for proven reserves to talk about other categories of reserves that, with the higher prices, can become economical.

Proven reserves, according to the American Petroleum Institute, are the "qualities of crude oil in the soil that geological and engineering data demonstrate with reasonable certainty that they are recoverable from known reservoirs, according to the technical and economic conditions of current operation" . In the statistics, proven reserves are usually cited.

Typically, the recovery rate of a field under exploration is low - on the order of 30-40 percent on average (the minimum is about 20 percent) - and the rest of the oil can only be extracted with the aid of recovery techniques. In addition, when a field is developed, reserve estimates are often corrected as the characteristics of the field become more precisely known. "The additional oil that can be recovered from an existing field in the form of a revaluation of reserves or through secondary or tertiary

recovery is called probable reserves." Adding the "proved" reserves to the "probable" reserves, we obtain the total discovered reserves.

It is also possible to estimate undiscovered reserves from geological evidence or other sophisticated techniques. Undiscovered reserves are called "possible reserves", and their existence and size are subject to great uncertainties. "Combining discovered and undiscovered reserves and assuming a 40 percent recovery factor, we get a number that is called 'recoverable' reserves.

Total oil reserves are a measure of the amount of oil believed to exist on Earth, leaving aside the question of the technical and economic viability of the recovery.

Many argue that as prices rise, probable reserves will become economical and prospecting for new fields will be stimulated. If the investment climate is favorable, this may be the case. But this says nothing about the limitations imposed by the lack of geological and engineering knowledge, the need for large capital investments, the availability of the necessary equipment and environmental considerations. In addition, the price will have to be high enough and appear on the market (that is, be free of government price controls). Finally, and most importantly, oil must actually exist to be discovered and exploited.

Measures will be taken to develop probable reserves and speed up prospecting; but progress may not be smooth, fast or inexpensive.

Recoverable reserves

The world's recoverable reserves are believed to be in the order of 1.6 trillion barrels; of that total, 37 percent or 608 billion barrels have already been discovered. The conversion of probable reserves to (proven reserves does not change the concentration of oil reserves that we mentioned earlier. Of the 608 billion barrels of discovered (most probable) reserves, 360 billion are located in the Middle East.

Total recoverable reserves (proven most likely but not discovered) in the Middle East are estimated at more than 510 billion barrels.

Oil consumption and demand

The advantages of oil as a fuel include:

- (1) Sufficient availability and, until recently, low price;
- (2) Ease of transportation;
- (3) Versatility and ease of replacing other energy sources. World oil consumption has quintupled in the past twenty-five years.

Factors that determine production levels include:

1. Population. Since countries with larger populations need higher incomes to ensure a minimum of economic and social investments, and thus maintain political stability and encourage economic development and self-sustained economic growth, highly populous countries need to maximize income from oil.

Although the size of the population undoubtedly has some influence on the need for oil income, the government's goals are linked more directly to income needs than to a simple population statistic. The more ambitious the government's goals for the country's future, the greater the income needs.

2. Structure of the Economy. If government goals can be met by income from various sources, the need for oil income will not be as pressing. Although it is unlikely that any producing country will agree to sell oil at a price lower than what it considers fair, the existence of other sources of income may allow a country to limit production in order to prolong the life of the reserves. Oil production as a percentage of the Gross National Product, the income of oil as a percentage of government revenue and oil exports as a percentage of total exports are indicators of the importance of oil in a given economy.

3. Development plans. The government's development plans, although in many OPEC countries budgets are rarely met, are an indication of the direction the nation's leaders would like to take and the prices they are willing to pay. Development plans make it possible to infer the need for imports and therefore the income needed to pay for these imports. They also indicate the possibilities and limitations of other sources of income. Thus, development plans can be important indicators of a country's future income needs.

4. Oil Reserves. Governments with lower reserves may be more cautious about permitted levels of production. To extend the life of the reserves, conservative production levels can be adopted. On the other hand, countries with larger reserves can produce more without compromising future production. A country with small reserves, but with good possibilities of developing alternative sources may prefer large production, even with the risk of depleting reserves, to finance the most promising economic saddles.

5. Prices. Price is also a very important factor. When prices are high, countries with small oil reserves can obtain an acceptable income with a relatively low level of production, thus releasing the government from the dilemma of choosing between conservation and the need to recipe. The structure of the oil market is also important. In a market with small idle capacity and in a situation of high demand, it is necessary to deliberately limit production.

None of these factors is deterministic, that is, although it may seem logical to an outside observer that an isolated factor should spell out production in a certain way, it is possible that, seen from a different point of view, the same factor implies another line of action.

Furthermore, the factors can have opposite influences. In fact, the factors suggested do not necessarily point to a single direction. Furthermore, the factors are not independent, so the actual levels of production will be determined by a complex combination of all these factors and others.

It is precisely a complex mixture of economic factors and political objectives that determines the now famous absorptive capacity, which, in turn, should determine production levels. A definition of absorptive capacity cannot be separate from the objectives of statesmen—from the opinions of leaders regarding the economic and political structure and role of their country, both internally and externally, including the importance attached to military spending. It will never be correct to say that a nation cannot use the funds generated by oil production to foster internal development, because the use of funds is linked to certain horizons and images in the minds of statesmen.

The increase in revenue helps to broaden these horizons. The increase in international influence is accompanied by more ambitious external goals, greater opportunities for adventure and greater international responsibilities.

Refining

Most international oil trade is done in the form of crude oil. Exports and imports of oil products are much less important, confirming the fact that most nations have opted for self-sufficiency in the refining sector.

Refined products represent only 15 percent of the world oil trade. These products accounted for 20 percent of US oil imports and the Antilles were the main supplier.

The United States, in turn, was responsible for more than 40 percent of world trade in oil products. Other industrialized countries are even less dependent on imports of refined products. Refineries are usually installed in close proximity to consumer markets, thus avoiding the need to use specialized vessels.

With the increase in refining capacity, the governments of the consuming countries were able to make use of the added value, and some countries even pay for the crude oil they import with profit.

The demand of refined products

The demand for refined products is concentrated in industrialized countries. North America, Western Europe and Japan accounted for 80 percent of the demand for refined petroleum products in (a total of 36,025,000 barrels per day for the three regions). In the same year, South America, the Middle East, Africa, the Far East and Oceania contributed only 20 percent. Refined product issues have much less to do with the level or increase in demand than with how that demand is met.

Refining capacity

Refining capacity is highly concentrated in developed countries. All regions are self-sufficient, except the United States.

However, if the Antilles refineries, of which they are the main consumer, are included, the United States becomes self-sufficient and even acquires idle capacity. In fact, all regions have considerable spare capacity. In the first half of 1980, North American refineries operated at about 85 percent of maximum capacity; Antilles refineries operated at 50 percent; those in Europe, at 60 percent; those in Japan, at 80 percent. On average, the world's refineries operated at about 75 percent of maximum capacity.

The increase in OPEC's refining capacity could do more. OPEC countries are finding it difficult to start the grandiose refinery projects that arose in the euphoria caused by high oil prices. The absolute numbers may be wrong, it may take longer than expected for these projects to be completed, but the trend seems clear

The world petroleum fleet and supply logistics

The world's tanker fleet is primarily responsible for transporting oil from producing regions to consumption centres. Of the nearly 32 MBD of crude oil and 5 MBD of petroleum products that make up international trade, approximately 95 percent are transported, at least in part, by an oil tanker. The suitability, ownership and control of the tanker fleet are therefore essential elements of energy geopolitics.

The suitability of the fleet refers to the ability to transport oil in sufficient quantities. In addition, the fleet can be assessed in terms of its ability to transport other sources of energy such as coal, which, although today of relatively little importance, may become more important in the international trade of the future. Finally, suitability can also be assessed in terms of the ability to serve certain locations; Suitability implies a certain flexibility to deal with unforeseen events, which require relocation.

Ownership and control issues involve the stated intention of oil-exporting countries to enter the oil industry's transportation sector and the consequences of change if it does occur. The volume of producer participation will be important; and the sectors in which they focus their activities will also be important.

A second consideration that results from the possible change in the ownership of the tanker fleet to oil-exporting countries.

As the oil trade occupies a prominent position in the world maritime trade (49 percent), oil transportation is important for the viability of national shipping industries.

In addition to the concern with the tanker fleet itself, but closely linked to supply logistics, there is the issue of the safety of maritime routes.

The concern with the safety of existing routes must be supplemented by an assessment of alternative routes and the implications for:

- (1) the defence of alternative routes and
- (2) the rapidity of oil supply if alternative routes are to be used.

Our analysis will focus on the following four areas:

Adequacy of the world tanker fleet

1. Fleet ownership and control
2. Safety of sea routes
3. Suitability and security of ports and terminals

Safety of maritime routes

The importance of sea routes from the Middle East to the United States, Western Europe and Japan is evident. More than 75 per cent of the active fleet of ocean tankers is committed to transporting oil from the Middle East to the rest of the world. In addition, 66 percent of the world's tanker fleet is engaged in transporting oil from the Middle East and North Africa to markets in the industrialized world, that is, the United States, Canada, Western Europe and Japan.

At the moment, the situation seems stable, but there is no guarantee that this state of affairs can evolve into serious events, with real dangers for the whole world. The conflict served to demonstrate the political fragility of the Arab states, apparently united around OPEC - when it comes to increasing the prices of this raw material and earning more profits but waging a muted struggle for dominance in the region.

If the Suez Canal were used to transport larger quantities of crude oil, oil tankers would not necessarily avoid the Straits of Hormuz. The Canal today does not seem to be a desirable route - freight is cheap, and the Canal is not suitable for large ships.